

PUBLICISTIC STYLE AND ITS FEATURES

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ABSTRACT

This article examines the publicist style, the language means used in it, about the general accessibility of this style, which is designed for a wide audience and should be understandable to everyone.

In today's world, the journalistic text is very popular, as almost all of us read newspapers, magazines, social networks to learn about the latest events and news in various spheres of human life. So, what is a publicist style, how does it differ from other types of text?

The function of the impact of language in the publicist style is in the foreground, it is associated with the functions of the message, information, as the interaction of the functions of impact and information due to the fact that the impact on public opinion through language relies on verbally expressed information about current events, the facts of current life - social, political, cultural, scientific, spiritual, economic, etc.

In their speech plan texts of a publicist nature conclude information about something - or a significant, essential, important. The publicist, reports on people, facts, events in different spheres of life, social and political forces involved in it. And, transmitting this or that information, necessarily gives it all an ideological interpretation, emotionally - expressive evaluation, in order to maximize the impact on the reader, his understanding of the world, consciousness, mood, his perception of the content of the journalistic text.

I.V. Arnold, in his book *Stylistics of Modern English*, says that "...a newspaper is a medium of information and a means of persuasion. It is designed for a mass and very heterogeneous audience, which it must retain, make itself read. The newspaper is usually read under conditions when it is rather difficult to concentrate: in the subway, on the train, at breakfast, resting after work, at lunchtime, filling up the short period of time vacated for some reason. Hence the need to organize the newspaper information so as to convey it quickly, concisely, to communicate the main point, even if the note will not be read to the end, and to have a certain emotional impact on the reader. The narrative should not require the reader to prepare in advance, and the dependence on context should be minimal. At the same time, along with the usual, constantly recurring topics, almost any topic appears in the newspaper that for some reason turns out to be relevant. Then these new situations and arguments also begin to repeat themselves. This repetition, as well as the fact that the journalist usually does

not have time to process the material thoroughly, leads to the frequent use of cliches. All of this creates the distinctive stylistic factors of the newspaper text" [1].

L.G. Kaida defines the characteristic of the speech system of the journalistic style as follows: "The inherent focus on impact and persuasion in journalistic works establishes a special relationship between the parties of communication - the speaker and the addressee of the speech. It is not stating, but imperative speech, it is designed not only to inform and not only to express the attitude to what is reported, but also to inspire this attitude in the addressee, i.e., in the final analysis, it is speech designed to influence the belief or behavior of the reader, its evaluation of those or other factors". [2].

Publicist style refers to the sphere of influential speech. And in this respect it is close in its functional purpose to political speech (a kind of oral public speech), to the language of radio, cinema and television speech. Together with the latter three, the journalistic style forms a block of so-called mass communication styles. The association of these styles can be regarded as a functional and stylistic sphere within the book speech. The unifying factor of the components of this sphere is the type of speech communication - mass information.

The most complete and consistent embodiment of the functional nature of the journalistic style, adequately reflecting the internal organization of its speech structure, is presented in the newspaper-publicistic style, or "newspaper language" - the most representative sub-style of the journalistic style [3]. In the journalistic style together with expressive speech elements there are standardized means of expression: clichés (they can be grouped into blocks), phrase utterances, signal words, speech stamps (an undesirable phenomenon in newspaper and generally in journalistic texts, because due to their "erased" semantic and expressive expressiveness they reduce the impact of the publicistic text on the recipient), etc.

The language of the newspaper distinguishes a number of standardized syntactic constructions: newspaper composition patterns frozen verbal formulas, general journalistic reproducible units. "Newspaper and journalistic styles are also characterized by the use of graphic means: typeface, headlines that should attract attention even from a distance, division into strips and distribution of one article on different pages increases the chance of each article catching the reader's eye, special headings for paragraphs" [4].

Publicist speeches are characterized by reliability, accuracy of facts, specificity, strict validity. This also brings it closer to the scientific style of speech.

As you can see, the journalistic style is filled with artistic and expressive means, various linguistic means, which make it accessible, understandable, accurate to a wide range of readers.

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